
The Web-Dynamics of Customer Engagement Influencing Retention in International Franchise Restaurant: A SEM Analysis

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the impact of website on customer retention in the International franchise restaurant industry in Bangladesh. The 210 survey responses were collected from university alumni using a randomized block design. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression models through IBM SPSS Statistics 26, then AMOS 25, to analyze factors of customer engagement to customer repurchase intention. The research was based on the U&G model and found that website features like interactivity, attractiveness, and content quality positively influence purchase intentions. The study highlights the importance of high-quality website content and interactive elements to build purchase intent, emphasizing the need for active and engaging social media. The findings contribute to International franchisee, policy makers and academicians in Bangladesh to develop their policy, ensure digital presence, boost revenue, and increase consumer engagement and revisit intentions.

KEYWORDS: Franchise, Restaurant, Revisit intention, Aesthetics. AMOS.

INTRODUCTION

In a franchise agreement, one party is granted the right to use intellectual property rights (IPR) of another party in exchange for a reward depending on the terms established by the other party. Urbanization, shifting lifestyles, and the impact of global culinary trends are driving increasing the demand for franchise food in Bangladesh. People of all ages love fast food because it's delicious, easy to make, and tasty. The multinational chain has become increasingly popular in Bangladesh, especially among younger generations, because to its prime location and modern eating experience. In addition, Bangladesh has moved up the UN development index from "least developed" to "lower middle income" in 2015 and then to "developing" in 2018, as stated by the UN (2019b). The nation has the lowest ranking 168 of South Asian economy in the ease of doing business index. recent political stability, market-driven economic policies, improved growth prospects, steady and expanding engagement in global commerce all contribute to Bangladesh's ability to become a significant economic power (Shafiq, 2019).

The economic liberalization and market opening have facilitated transformative changes in consumer preferences and behaviors. Purchase intentions, which are indicative of consumers' propensity to acquire a product, are intricately linked to their attitudes. One of the first franchise chains open in India was KFC. Its inaugural Bangalore store opened in June 1995 (Prasad, 2015). In contrast to Pakistan, where the inaugural Pizza Hut franchise opened in 1993, India experienced its inauguration after 2 years (India Brand Equity Foundation, 2019b). Later, the Bangladeshi people was finally welcomed by Pizza Hut in late 2003, after a ten-year wait (Haque et al., 2023). According to franchise experts, the Bangladeshi market is expected to expand at a faster pace than India's and attain a value of \$6–7 billion within the next 6–7 years (Daily Star, 2018b). The Bangladesh Trademark Act of 2009 (WIPO, 2009) allows international individuals or companies to register their trademarks in order to protect them within the domain of intellectual property law. Because the franchise industry has recently shown interest in developing and emerging markets around the world, academic studies on franchising have begun to centre on these regions (Dant & Grunhagen, 2014).

Interestingly, the country's middle class is growing at a rapid pace and is a major contributor to the GDP per capita, which was \$3,879.20 in 2018. In contrast, when discretionary incomes have dropped and spending habits have changed as a result of the pandemic's economic consequences and customers, people now are concerned more about their health. Despite this, maintaining a positive online reputation by overcoming negative reviews and leveraging e-WOM to enhance customer retention remains a challenge. The objective of this study is to examine the impact of website on customer retention at franchise restaurants in Bangladesh. It is vital that this study offers stakeholders such as policymakers, and public health organizations valuable insights on a website's aesthetics, personalization, trustworthiness, and retention in context with Bangladesh. Social media, online reviews, and loyalty programs are all examples of digital engagement tactics that this study delves into in detail to show how they

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affect client retention. For marketers and franchise managers looking to maximize their digital initiatives, this information is vital. The second important takeaway for worldwide franchises doing business in different areas is the study's emphasis on cultural sensitivity in customer interaction strategies. The research contributes to the current corpus of knowledge in the field by offering a comprehensive framework for assessing digital engagement by incorporating concepts from customer relationship management and web dynamics.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Underpinning

While atmospherics are a part of the computer interface in an online setting, nothing is currently known about how this interface influences customers' intents to make purchases (Richard, 2005). The proposed hypothesized model is based on the Uses and Gratification (U&G) theory to analyze the factors influencing customer retention through website engagement. U&G theory posits that individuals actively seek out media that meet their various needs, including information, entertainment, and social interaction. This theory helps explain why customers engage with restaurant websites and how these engagements fulfill their needs, ultimately influencing their retention. Within the framework of traditional media, U&G's research has been useful in explaining customer actions and worries. Numerous studies have utilized U&G inside the framework of the internet (Ko et al., 2005). Second, the features of the website make virtual environments that are more enjoyable for online buyers. This study's theoretical model follows the U&G paradigm, which holds that consumers' engagement with franchise restaurants is the first component and that consumers' intentions to buy from foreign franchise restaurants in Bangladesh constitute the third component. It follows that figure 1 represents the suggested model.

Customer trust (CT) is a sentiment of assurance experienced by consumers during their engagement with a brand. Researchers found website interactivity as essential for banks to improve overall performance (Utami, et al., 2022). However, there is a lack of empirical investigation into the influence of interactivity on customer engagement as clients require interactive website in other services institutions like franchise restaurant (Khan, et al., 2023). Website aesthetics, which includes fonts, colors, photos, shapes, animation, and music, can positively impact users' perception of a website and facilitate communication. In addition, customer testing helps restaurants understand which communication channels and messages resonate best with their audience (Rasli, et al., 2022). Furthermore, personalization offers evidence that is specifically suited to the user, and using personalization features helps create products and services of unique value to individuals (NSO, 2018; Wessel & Thies, 2015). Interactivity boosts engagement in Western markets, according to Wu et al. (2021), but its impact is less obvious in underdeveloped nations like Bangladesh, where people may prefer less complicated interfaces. While aesthetics plays a vital role in customer retention, the former's impact on satisfaction and the latter's suitability for a given region's users might vary widely. The apparent benefits of personalization could be limited if customers fail to appreciate its immediate and relevant value. Honesty and consideration of cultural differences are crucial for personalization projects to gain customers' trust (Chowdhury et al., 2023; Chaffey & Smith, 2019). While Davis et al. (2021) found that ease of use was a substantial predictor of consumer satisfaction in technologically advanced countries, other qualities, such trust and accessibility, may have a greater impact in developing regions.

Trust plays a significant role in consumers' purchase intentions, as it is a key factor in online environments and social media communities. Consumer confidence in online shopping websites is influenced by their popularity and reliability. Purchasing decisions involve individuals evaluating various choices and making a purchase decision to meet their needs (Zhao et al., 2019). In the field of marketing, consumer trust is determined by the consumer's intention to revisit a brand, as per Ramanathan (2017). One of the most significant challenges in marketing today involves regaining faith in the franchise food industry among consumers.

Crucially, Gutjar et al. (2015) discovered that people's positive emotions were more strongly linked with their meal choices than their preferences, and that negative emotions were more strongly linked with their food preferences. Customers can expect consistency from worldwide fast food businesses because of the identical menus, quick service, and friendly staff at each location. Their fast food eating experience becomes more predictable and satisfying as a result (Ozdemir & Ergin, 2017).

Expanding upon the aforementioned study assertions, following hypotheses were proposed:

- H1. Customer interactivity has positive relationship with customer trust;
- H2. Customer aesthetics has positive relationship with customer trust;
- H3. Customer ease of use has a positive correlation with customer trust;
- H4. Customer test has positive relationship with customer trust;
- H5. Customer personalization has positive relationship with customer trust and
- H6: Customer trust has positive relationship with customer retention

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Figure1: Hypothesized theoretical model

METHODS

The demographic profile refers to the characteristics and attributes of a certain population or group, such as age, gender, and profession. Among the 210 responses received, it was observed that 30% (n = 63) corresponded to females, while the remaining 70% (n =147) corresponded to males. Furthermore, 39.5% (n = 83) of the individuals belonged to the age group of 25s, while 60.5% (n = 127) were in their 35s possessed a bachelor's degree, along with an income ranging from 50k to above per month. Finally, out of the total respondents 24% (n = 51) were service holders,21%(n=44) housewives, and 55% (n=115) merchants.

Sample and data collection

Convenient sampling is employed to obtain prompt replies and makes it simple for researchers to contact respondents who are accessible from mall intercept interview from thirty residents of Chattogram during January to February, 2024. The researcher thereafter made modifications based on the residents' feedback. After making the required edits, the survey questions were sent out to members of the private university alumni network via Google forms using a randomized block design method for sampling. The survey contains of questions with multiple choices and five-point Likert scale (Sugiyono,2012) ratings through online survey. The measurement of items was adapted from the previous study (McLean, 2018; Mahmoud's, 2019). Among the 236 replies collected, a total of 22 were deemed incomplete and hence eliminated from subsequent analysis. For further analysis, the 210 survey questionnaires that were received are cited in IBM SPSS Statistics 26 and MS Excel 2016. In the end, 210 responses were chosen (which represents a 95% confidence level, a 5% margin of error, 50% population proportion, and an unlimited population size) which is sufficient for the study(Krejcie & Morgan, 1970).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Demographic Profile

The demographic profile refers to the characteristics and attributes of a certain population or group, such as age, gender,income and profession. Descriptive statistics were used to assess and analyze the responder demographic.

Table 1 Background characteristic

Variable	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	74	35.2
Female	136	64.8
Age		
<25	40	19.1
26-35	104	49.5
35>above	66	31.4
Education		
Undergraduate	48	22.9

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Masters	153	72.8
Alumni	9	4.3
Occupation		
Unemployed or homemaker	79	37.6
Student	12	5.7
Pvt.Sector Employee	85	40.5
Public Sector Employee	18	8.6
Self Employed	16	7.6
Monthly Family Income		
Below Tk 25000	0	0
25001 to 50000 Tk.	95	45.2
50001 to 75000 Tk.	62	29.5
75000 to 100000 Tk.	40	19.5
Tk.100000 or above	13	5.8

In table 1, of the valid respondents, 112 are men and 88 are women; the age distribution is as follows: Furthermore, 19% (n = 40) of the individuals belonged to the age group of 25s, while 49% (n = 104) were in their 35s and others are over 35. According to the demographics, approximately 73.5 percent of the participants had an education level higher than the SSC. There are 41 responders who have finished post-graduation (39.4%), with only six (5.8%) holding a professional degree. Among the 210 responses received, it was observed that 65% (n = 136) corresponded to females, while the remaining 35% are males (n =35.2). Finally, out of the total respondents 49% (n = 103) were service holders,37%(n=79) housewives, and 7.6% (n=16) merchants or self-employed.

4.2 The Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Statistical tests for the hypotheses were carried out using SPSS for exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and AMOS 26 for structural equation modeling (SEM). Keeping this in mind, the EFA was administered using the principal rotation approach and a total of 21 test items. The findings indicate that the sampling adequacy measure, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure, was higher than .60, and the Bartlett's Test of sphericity is statistically significant at $p < .001$ (Hair et al., 2014). These findings support the suitability of the EFA, as the KMO value of 0.880 in this investigation is quite appropriate for factor analysis. Besides, a five-factor structure is suggested by the pattern matrix's output. The five components also accounted for 70.30 percent of the total variance in the analysis, and their eigenvalues were greater than 1. Similarly, with cronbach's alpha values higher than .70, the reliability of the scale items for all variables is considered adequate (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). Aesthetics (.72), usability (.80), customer test (.78), personalization (.83), and trust (.84) are the variables with which interactivity has a coefficient alpha of .79.

We choose the SEM because it can analyse individual equations and numerous equations at the same time. It gives a way to change the model, makes plausible fit indices, and calculates the residual errors for each indicator (Hair et al., 2014; Bryne, 2016).

4.3 Measurement Assessment

To verify findings of the exploratory factor analysis, as well as to evaluate the construct reliability and validity, the measurement model was utilized. An examination of the constructs' internal reliability revealed cronbach's alpha values between 0.78 to 0.96, which is higher than the minimum threshold of 0.70 (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). In this case, 0.784 is the factor loading with the lowest value seen. According to Hair et al. (2014), a high level of convergent validity is shown by standardized loadings that are greater than .50. According to Bagozzi and Yi (1988), all of the latent variables have sufficient internal consistency reliability with composite reliability values above .70. Due to the sensitive nature of Cronbach alpha to the quantity of test instruments, composite reliability is deemed slightly the best measure of construct reliability in the measurement model (Hair et al., 2014).

The model and data were also tested using AMOS 25. Testing for convergent validity was done by looking at the latent variables' factor loadings. Table 2 displays the related average variance extracted AVE and composite reliability.

Table 2 Findings of Psychometric Measures

Variables	CR	MSV	AVE	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Interactivity(1)	.80	.520	.67	(0.882)	-	-	-			
Aesthetics(2)	.72	.580	.63	0.476	(0.834)	-	-			
Ease of use(3)	.80	.580	.62	0.434	0.456	(0.852)	-			
Customer Test(4)	.85	.262	.68	0.428	0.412	0.512	(0.812)			
Personalize (5)	.83	.474	.63	0.367	0.423	0.455	0.424	(0.810)		

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Customer Trust(6)	.81	.472	.69	0.423	0.455	0.428	0.412	0.512	(0.812)
Repurchase intention(7)	.85	.354	.61	0.428	0.412	0.367	0.423	0.455	0.424 (0.810)

Notes: CR = Composite Reliability; MSV = Maximum Shared Variance; AVE = Average Variance Extracted. Source: Calculated from survey data. * P < 1%; Source: SPSS 26

Composite reliability was used to evaluate the construct reliability, while discriminant validity and convergent validity were validated using Fornell and Lacker's criterion and average variance extracted (AVE), respectively (Bagozzi & Yi, 1998; Hair et al., 2014). According to Fornell and Lacker (1981), all of the latent variables in Table 3 had AVEs above .50, ranging from .61 to .69, indicating high convergent validity.

4.4 Structural Model Assessment

The SEM structural model was used for further validation in order to corroborate all assumptions and measure the significant levels of correlations between variables. Table 3 and Figure 2 show the outcomes of the hypotheses. The Bentler-Bonett index (GFI = 0.956, CFI = 0.957, TLI = 0.941, NFI = 0.926) shows that all five variables tested have values greater than 0.90. The previous results indicate that the measurement model has excellent convergent validity during the mono-method analysis stage.

Figure 2 : Structural model of the output

Source: AMOS output

Table 3 Results of hypotheses

Paths	Beta (β)	Std Error	P-values	Decisions
H1: Interactivity → Customer Trust	0.54	.048	.027	Supported
H2 : Aesthetics → Customer Trust	0.35	.056	.022	Supported
H3 :Ease of use → Customer Trust	0.44	.121	.015	Supported
H4 :Customer test → Customer Trust	0.24	.097	.012	Supported
H5 :Personalize→ Customer Trust	0.34	.131	.021	Supported
H6:Customer Trust→Retention	0.36	.136	.024	Supported

The regression weight (path coefficient) between the Interactivity (IN) and Customer Trust (CT) is significant and positive ($\beta=0.54$; $p < 0.05$), which firmly confirms that apps interactivity has a positive influences on customer engagement. This finding supports previous studies (Hari, et al., 2022; Sivakumar, & Ganeshkumar,2022). The regression weight for aesthetics to customer engagement is 0.35 with p-value 0.022, which is less than 0.05. Thus H2 is supported with previous studies (Zahra & Usman, 2022; Ahmed, & Zainuldin,2022).The path coefficient for ease of use to customer engagement is 0.44 with p-value 0.015, which is less than 0.05.

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So ease of use has significant contribution to customer engagement. Thus, H3 is supported with previous studies (Qadri, et al., 2023). Furthermore, H4 is supported as the regression weight shows relations with customer test to customer trust is 0.24 with p-value 0.012 ($\beta=.24, p < 0.05$) with previous studies (Abror, et al., 2020). H5 is supported as the regression weight shows relations with customization or personalization to customer trust is 0.34 with p-value 0.021 ($\beta=.34, p < 0.05$) with previous studies Mobile apps contents of KFC positively affect customer trust and aligns with prior studies (Islam, et al., 2016; Islam & Rahman, 2017; Fauzi & Suryani, 2019). H6 is supported as the regression weight shows relations with customer Trust to revisit intention is 0.24 with p-value 0.012 ($\beta=.24, p < 0.05$) with previous studies. Previous research in the services sector (e.g., Mahmoud, 2019; Febrian, et al., 2021) has been supported by these results.

Five of the variables (interactivity, aesthetics, ease of use, customer test, personalization) had a statistically significant effect on the customer retention. Each of construct was assessed using a minimum of three items for the purpose of data analysis. It is worth noting that prior studies primarily concentrated on customers of websites with a particular emphasis on non-university students (Yeo, et al., 2022), in contrast this study focuses on alumni students of selected private universities in Chattogram of Bangladesh. In addition, the study showed that the measurement model's fit indices are all within acceptable limits, indicating a decent overall fit. In this study, the factor loadings that were analyzed in the confirmatory factor analysis were found to be greater than 0.50, and the composite reliability, which is determined by the maximum shared variance, was found to be greater than 0.70.

CONCLUSION

This study examines the characteristics of websites that increase repurchases intention, with a specific focus on the millennial demographic in Bangladesh. The model is composed of 21 components and six hypotheses, which were further investigated using data from millennial participants who were active on websites. The SEM's global fit criteria suggest that this model is preferable. Hierarchical measurement models are encouraged to be employed more frequently in future studies of e-service quality, as this hierarchy has been the subject of so few studies thus far. The objective of the research is to determine the factors that contribute to the franchise industry in Bangladesh and the influence of website design on consumer engagement, trust, and retention. According to the findings, four of the constructs investigated in this investigation are statistically significant, and one of the constructs (customer engagement) has a mediating relationship with repurchase intention. The conceptualization model proposed by Blut et al. (2015) is evaluated in the study, which demonstrates that a variety of factors related to website design must be taken into account. The study contributes to the current corpus of knowledge on online customer interaction by investigating the importance of websites in the context of franchise restaurants in Bangladesh. In order to provide a more comprehensive picture of the elements impacting fast food consumers' attitudes, future research can expand on this study's focus on a few specific aspects.

Although there is a strong relationship between website design and consumer satisfaction, repurchase intention, and positive word of mouth, it is logical to assume that customers are more likely to pay more for outstanding service. Online Customers are often thought to be more price-conscious than those who shop in physical stores, thus researchers might consider looking into their propensity to pay in these circumstances in the future.

The data acquired in this study came from university alumni students, and as a result, it may not be representative of the entire population. Consequently, the generalizability of the study's conclusions is restricted. Data from a more representative sample of website users should be collected in future research.

Convenience and mood were identified as significant factors in the development of a positive attitude towards KFC, with a highly significant effect. It illustrates that respondents associate fast food consumption with improved moods and perceived it as a practical option for quick meals. Furthermore, an attitude was also influenced by social influence and satisfaction; however, satisfaction was the only factor that had a statistically significant positive impact. Social influence has a detrimental impact on attitudes; however, it is not statistically significant at conventional levels, indicating that it may not be a significant factor in the formation of attitudes. They also desire that KFC implement more appealing promotions or loyalty programs for customers and provide a broader selection of healthy menu options to accommodate a variety of dietary preferences. Additionally, consumers desire to maintain their association with KFC.

The current marketing literature on consumer behaviour in an online environment, particularly for e-commerce and s-commerce, is greatly enhanced by this research study. First, this research provides a fresh take on the topic by looking at how s-commerce constructs affect web design and how "Use and gratification theory" explains why people shop online. This work adds to the expanding corpus of literature on "Use and gratification theory" by giving it an important role in the field and expanding its theoretical application to the online environment, particularly for social media applications such as s-commerce constructs. Secondly, it backs up the prior theoretical framework for social commerce adoption with empirical evidence. The widespread use

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of area development franchising can be ascribed to franchisors' aim to decrease the quantity of franchise contracts in order to save transaction and agency expenses..

The goal of our investigation was to fill a research gap regarding the impact of factors of franchise websites and brand repurchases intention. Our research showed that customers' perceptions of franchise food brand and their propensity to buy it again are shaped by the interplay between brand awareness and customer engagement which was influenced by customer trust with the brand. No prior research has examined this connection. Consequently, this investigation's principal contribution is to probe this hitherto uncharted combination of variables. Nonetheless, the results of this study demonstrate its reliability. Therefore, this research framework is distinctive, particularly in the context of the mobile industry.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. The findings of this study suggest that business managers should prioritize creating awareness and cultivating a positive brand image for their website in their marketing activities.
- ii. KFC and other fast food chains would do well to put money into creating new menu items that cater to people who are concerned about their health. Things like fresh juices, grilled chicken, and salads could be on the menu. Businesses can appeal to customers who are concerned about their health and meet their preferences by emphasizing these possibilities.
- iii. To capitalize on this factor, KFC should continue to enhance the convenience of its services, including online ordering, delivery, and effective payment options.
- iv. To preserve its market position and customer base, KFC must identify the factors that influence customers' positive attitudes and encourage them to return to its outlets. It is imperative that KFC constantly monitors these factors, as they are subject to change over time.
- v. KFC should persist in its investment in effective marketing campaigns in order to capitalize on the influence of social channels. In order to improve the social influence factor that influences consumer decisions, KFC should implement a variety of effective strategies. The following strategies are employed: nurturing positive word of mouth, utilizing social media endorsements, and promoting user-generated content.
- vi. Attractive loyalty programs may be implemented by KFC to enhance purchase intentions. KFC may incentivize repeat business and exploration of new menu items by providing discounts, meal deals, or other incentives to its most loyal consumers
- vii. KFC should think about tailoring its marketing to certain markets due to the wide variety of customer demographics. For example, menu items that are nutritious may be prioritized in promotions that are designed to appeal to elderly consumers.
- viii. KFC may explore the possibility of establishing partnerships or collaborations with programs or organizations that promote active lifestyles and healthful eating.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The author has not declared any conflict of interests.

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